

Deliverable 1.1

Project Quality Management Plan PQMP

Dissemination level		
PU	Public — fully open (automatically posted online)	X
SEN	Sensitive — limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	

Cover and Control Page of Document	
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¹ **DATA** = data sets, **DEC** = Websites, patent filings, videos, etc; **DEM** = Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, **ETHICS**; **OTHER**; **R** = Document, report.

Disclaimer

This deliverable is based on the project Grant Agreement, Consortium Agreement, relevant guidelines by the European Commission, and the VTT general template for Project Quality Management Plan.

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Abbreviations

AB	Advisory Board
CA	Consortium Agreement
CINEA	European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
CO	Project Coordinator (VTT)
DoA	Description of Action, project plan (Annex 1 Part B of the GA)
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
GenA	General Assembly (in ADMIRAL project)
HE	Horizon Europe
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
MC	Management Committee (in ADMIRAL project)
PO	Project Officer, representative of the funding agency CINEA
PQMP	Project Quality Management Plan (the deliverable at hand)
RP	Reporting Period
TL	Task Leader
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Executive Summary

The deliverable D1.1 *Project Quality Management Plan PQMP* is an introduction to the ADMIRAL project as well as its management and practicalities that is intended to serve as a guidebook for the consortium throughout the project lifetime. The primary target group of this deliverable is the project partners and the individual team members involved in ADMIRAL.

The goal of the deliverable is to ensure the high-quality management of the project and uniformity in the project activities. The deliverable describes, for example, the consortium composition, organisational structure and decision-making processes, financial management, internal procedures for deliverable preparation and other reporting practices, as well as risk prevention and mitigation. Moreover, the deliverable presents the lists of key contact persons, defines the working procedures, and provides information on the project templates.

The deliverable is based on the ADMIRAL Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement, which set the legal framework of the project. While the deliverable refers to the Grant or Consortium Agreements, it does not replace or overrule either of them in any circumstance. Rather, the deliverable highlights key sections of the Agreements by providing instructions on the practical ways of working and management in the project. Should there be any discrepancies between the project documentation, the following order always prevails: (1) Grant Agreement, (2) Consortium Agreement, (3) Project Quality Management Plan.

Due to the guiding role of the deliverable, it is to be considered a living document that can be updated throughout the project lifecycle as needed. The responsibility of updating the document remains with the Coordinator, while the partners are expected to actively propose ways to improve the cooperation and this document. Should any consortium member have any suggestions for updates or additions, they are requested to be in contact with the Coordinator Team. The latest version of the deliverable will always be available in the document repository of the project.

1 Introduction

The present deliverable D1.1 Project Quality Management Plan PQMP serves as a practical introduction to ADMIRAL as well as the jointly agreed working practices to ensure the high-quality management of the project. This plan outlines the framework for the project implementation, including internal communication, means of progress monitoring, reporting practices, risk management, and other central aspects of the project.

This deliverable is created as part of Work Package 1 *Management* which aims at ensuring the good overall management, administration, coordination, and execution of the project, and that the project progresses, and results are achieved in accordance with the Grant Agreement (GA) and expectations of the call. More specifically, the deliverable is part of Task 1.2 *Coordination and project management* which sets the operational coordination activities at consortium level, from overall day-to-day management to monitoring and supervising the project activities in different WPs. The WP is also connected to Task 1.1 *Financial and administrative management* in a way that the management of funding, keeping records, and complying with the funding rules are introduced in this deliverable as well.

The aim of this deliverable is, most importantly, to ensure i) the management of project-related documentation, ii) the monitoring and quality control of project deliverables and milestones, and iii) sound risk contingency management. The content of the deliverable has been drafted by the Coordinator (CO) as leader of WP1. Accordingly, the CO is responsible for updating the document whenever necessary.

The target audience of the deliverable is all the project members who may work for ADMIRAL during its duration. While the consortium members are expected to carefully read the deliverable and comply with the set rules herein, the consortium members also have an active role in developing the deliverable further. Should any consortium member have suggestions for improvements or questions about the deliverable, they are encouraged to contact the CO team promptly. The contact details of the team are listed in Section 3.2 of this document.

The PQMP is intended to complement the project Grant and Consortium Agreements and provide concrete details on how to properly implement the project. In case of inconsistency between the documents, however, the following order of precedence should be applied: (1) Grant Agreement, (2) Consortium Agreement, (3) PQMP.

2 ADMIRAL in short

ADMIRAL is a three-year Innovation Action (IA) project funded by the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). The project brings together 20 beneficiaries and one Affiliated Entity from all over Europe to transform the freight transportation industry with a systemic socio-technical approach. ADMIRAL aims to change the general mindset to take the emission level minimisation as the main target by providing tools for companies. The main result is the Admiral

marketplace, which manages the whole supply chain infrastructure and related emissions. It also works as a channel for developers to distribute innovative and sustainability-focused solutions in EU.

More information about the project is available in the Grant Agreement and on the project website www.admiral-project.eu. The general project information is summarised in Table 1.

Table 1 General project information

Project name	Advanced multimodal marketplace for low emission and energy transportation
Acronym	ADMIRAL
Call and topic	HORIZON-CL5-2022-D6-02-01
Type of the action	HORIZON Innovation Action
Grant Agreement no.	101104163
Start and end date	01.05.2023 – 30.04.2026
Project duration	36 months
Max. grant amount	7 294 412,14 €

The project is organised into seven Work Packages (WP) which structure the research, pilot, marketplace development, management as well as communication, dissemination and exploitation work in the project. Each WP is led by a designated organisation. The details of the WPs are listed in Table 2.

Table 2: List of ADMIRAL Work Packages

No.	WP title	Activity type	WP Leader	Start and end month
WP1	Management	Management	VTT	M1 – M36
WP2	Sustainable development of logistics & transport	Research	LNEC	M1 – M32
WP3	Business models for sustainable transports	Research	VTT	M1 – M23
WP4	Multimodal marketplace development	Research	AWA	M1 – M36
WP5	Pilots	Research	VTT	M2 – M32
WP6	Assessment of solutions and impact assessment	Research	CTLup	M13 – M36
WP7	Communication, dissemination and exploitation	Other	Steinbeis	M1 – M36

A more detailed description of each WP and its Tasks is given in Annex I of the Grant Agreement. In addition to these seven WPs, there are also the ethics requirements that are to be carefully considered throughout the project in all phases of research, management, dissemination, and other activities.

3 Consortium in short

3.1 Beneficiaries

The ADMIRAL consortium consists of 20 Beneficiaries and one Affiliated Entity. These form the Consortium Partners. The Consortium Partners and their main representatives are listed in Table 3.

Table 3 List of Beneficiaries and Affiliated Entity

No.	WP title	Acronym	Country	Main contact person
B1	VTT Technological Research Centre of Finland Ltd.	VTT	Finland	Harri Pyykkö
B2	AWAKE.AI OY	AWA	Finland	Karno Tenovuo
B3	Laboratorio Nacional de Engenharia Civil	LNEC	Portugal	Elisabete Arsenio
B4	Universidad Politecnica de Madrid	UPM	Spain	José Manuel Vassallo Magro
B5	Univerza V Ljubljani	UL	Slovenia	Patricija Bajec
B6	Steinbeis Innovation gGmbH	Steinbeis	Germany	Meike Reimann
B7	Transporto Inovaciju Asociacija	TIA	Lithuania	Inga Ablingienė
B8	Steveco Oy	STE	Finland	Heikki Jääskeläinen
B9	Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis	CERTH	Greece	Georgia Ayfantopoulou
B10	CTLup SRL	CTLup	Italy	Sevket Oguz Kagan Capkin
B11	Posta Slovenje DOO	PS	Slovenia	Alen Kahvedžić
B12	UAB Normalis Teach	NORM	Lithuania	Ieva Markucevičiūtė
B13	Solvesall Inteligentne Restive DOO	SOLV	Slovenia	Luka Bradesko
B14	Trevio UAB	Trevio	Lithuania	Dainius Berškys
B15	UAB CargoGo Logistics	CargoGo	Lithuania	Lauras Pranckevičius
B16	Cargo Sign, UAB	Csign	Lithuania	Rytis Rudelis
B17	Locodels DOO	Locod	Croatia	Davor Justament
AE17.1	Croatian Post	HP	Croatia	Tamara Bonković
B18	Marloconsult LDA	MARLO	Portugal	João Graça
B19	APS – Administracao dos portos de Sines e do Algarve, S.A.	APS	Portugal	Luís Miguel Silva
B20	UAB Klapeidos laisvosios ekonomines zonos valodymo bendrove	KLEZ	Lithuania	Darius Butvydas

3.2 Main contact persons at Consortium level

The people in charge of various project-related tasks are listed in Table 4.

Table 4 Main project contact persons

Role	Organisation	Main contact	Deputy
Coordinator	VTT	Harri Pyykkö	
Coordinator support, WP5 Leader	VTT	Ville Hinkka	
Administrative support	VTT	Camilla Halinoja	
Financial support	VTT	Suvi Järvinen	
Data Manager	VTT	Jukka Kääriäinen	
WP1 Leader	VTT	Harri Pyykkö	Camilla Halinoja
WP2 Leader	LNEC	Elisabete Arsenio	José Barateiro
WP3 Leader	VTT	Markku Mikkola	Jukka Kääriäinen
WP4 Leader	AWA	Karno Tenovuo	Simo Salminen
WP5 Leader	VTT	Ville Hinkka	-
WP6 Leader	CTLup	Sevket Oguz Kagan Capkin	Davide Shingo Usami
WP7 Leader	Steinbeis	Meike Reimann	Patrik Schumacher
Pilot Leader PT/ES	APS	Luís Miguel Silva	Isabel Alves
Pilot Leader SI/HR	PS	Alen Kahvedžić	TBC
Pilot Leader LT	TIA	Inga Ablingienė	Asta Kazliuskiene
Pilot Leader FIN	Steveco	Heikki Jääskeläinen	Niklas Anckar

The contact details of the mentioned people as well as the full list of all the Consortium members and their contact information can be found in the designated ADMIRAL contact persons Excel file which is stored in the project Teams Group. **All organisations are responsible for keeping their contact details up to date and informing the CO in case of any changes.**

4 Project management

4.1 Organisational structure and decision-making

The **organisational structure** and management procedures of the project have been defined in accordance with all partners in the proposal phase and then transferred to the Grant and Consortium Agreements and this document accordingly. The descriptions of consortium bodies and decision-making processes mentioned in this document intend to summarise the roles and responsibilities. A

detailed description of each Consortium body, their duties and responsibilities can be found in the CA, which binds all members of the Consortium.

In sum, the main management organs of the project are the **General Assembly (GenA)**, **Management Committee (MC)**, and **Advisory Board (AB)**. These are led by the **Coordinator (CO)**, VTT, which has a major role in the daily management and acts as the legal entity intermediate between the Parties and the Funding Agency. In addition, the project work is led by **WP Leaders (WPL)**. The duties of the CO and WPLs, as well as the roles and composition of each management body, are depicted next.

4.1.1 Coordinator

The **CO** of the project, VTT, leads the consortium by performing the tasks assigned to it as described in the Grant Agreement (GA) and in the Consortium Agreement (CA). One of the core tasks of the CO is to **represent the project consortium** towards the funding agency CINEA and the Project Officer (PO). Please note that only the CO should communicate with the PO. Should any beneficiary come across issues that might need to be raised to the awareness of the PO, they should immediately inform the CO who takes necessary actions.

In addition to the liaison role, the CO is responsible for the operational coordination activities at the consortium level, such as the overall **day-to-day coordination of the project**, monitoring and supervision of activities concerning deliverables, milestones and periodic reports as well as arranging for shared virtual workspaces and internal working procedures. Moreover, the CO will manage the project's administrative, financial, and legal activities as a part of the Management and Coordination WP.

VTT has extensive experience in various EU projects, and it has a unique EU team, which supports project managers of EU-funded projects in all financial and administrative aspects during the lifecycle of the project. VTT's legal counsels together with the project Beneficiaries have prepared the CA, and the Non-Disclosure Agreements (NDAs) for the AB members. The legal and administrative teams will also advise on all contractual and IPR matters.

In ADMIRAL, the designated CO Team consists of

- Coordinator: Harri Pyykkö
- Coordinator Support: Ville Hinkka
- Senior EU Project Specialist: Camilla Halinoja
- Financial Coordinator: Suvi Järvinen

Whenever contacting the CO Team, please always include Harri, Ville and Camilla as recipients of your email. If the matter concerns financial issues, please assign your email to Suvi and include at least Harri and Camilla in copy of the email.

4.1.2 Work Package Leaders

As mentioned in the introduction, the work of the ADMIRAL project is divided into seven WPs. Each WP is led by a designated representative and organization called the **WPL**. The WPLs and details of the WPs are listed in Table 4.

The WPLs are responsible for the progress of the work conducted in their WPs, including ensuring that the work progresses as planned, enhancing the collaboration and finding synergies in the technical and scientific nature of the work, and preparing the designated deliverables. The WPLs also serve as the main contact point for the activities in their WP, answering to, e.g., the reporting requests of the CO.

The WPLs are expected to coordinate the work that needs to be conducted in their WP and communicate of the progress to the CO and the rest of the consortium.

The coordination of WPs includes, e.g.,

- participating to the monthly MC meetings and providing an overview of the advancement of the work
- organising regular WP meetings to keep track of the progress and agree on work distribution.
 - Organising meetings includes, e.g., sending the meeting invitations with designated agendas, taking minutes of the meetings, and distributing the meeting material promptly for the use of the WP members.
 - More details on the organisation of meetings can be found in section 4.2 Working practices.
- conducting and overseeing the composition of the deliverables and other reporting material related to their WP. The CO will help with this task by reminding them of the deliverables' schedules and submitting the deliverable to the EU portal.

In case a WP includes Tasks that are led by another organization than the WPL, the WPL is responsible for agreeing on the work practices with the **Task Leader (TL)**. The distribution of Tasks to TLs can be found in the GA. The TLs cooperate with the WPLs with the aim of meeting the set goals. In case any issues emerge, the TL must rapidly inform the WP leader and CO who, in turn, take necessary actions. The role and responsibilities of the TL will be defined in more detail as the project progresses.

4.1.3 General Assembly

The **GenA** is the ultimate decision-making body of the Consortium. Its role and responsibilities derive from the ADMIRAL CA (drafted upon the Horizon Europe DESCA CA template) which has been signed by all beneficiaries.

The GenA operates according to the following principles based on the CA:

- each GenA member shall have one vote
- the GenA shall not deliberate and decide validly unless two-thirds of the members are present or represented
- the responsibilities and authority of the GenA shall be set out in the Consortium Agreement (CA), including
 - content, finances, and intellectual property rights
 - evolution of the Consortium,
 - actions required for non-performing or underperforming participants,
 - processes relating to the coordination of IPR management and the distribution of EU funding.

The detailed decision-making procedures in the CA aim to minimise the risk of problems arising during the implementation of the project. The mechanisms for the resolution of any emerging conflicts will be resolved based on the CA procedures.

The GenA consists of one official representative of each consortium member and a deputy representative who shall represent the official member in case of absence. Both representatives are welcome to participate in the meeting, but only one vote will be counted per Beneficiary. The CO manages the GenA's actions, including organising and chairing the meetings.

The composition of the GenA was confirmed in the first GenA meeting which was held in Espoo, Finland, on the 3rd of May 2023. The list of GenA members and deputies can be found in the ADMIRAL consortium contact list Excel as well as the GenA meeting slides.

4.1.4 Management Committee

The **MC** is the primary day-to-day managerial organ that is responsible for supervising the operational tasks and decisions to be made in ADMIRAL. The MC oversees the project activities, including executing the overall research plan (GA Annex I). The MC is formed by the CO, the WPLs, and pilot leaders, and it shall report and be accountable to the GenA.

The composition of the MC was confirmed in the first GenA meeting which was held in Espoo, Finland, on the 3rd of May 2023. The list of MC members and deputies can be found in the ADMIRAL consortium contact list Excel as well as the GenA meeting slides.

The MC works mainly via online or in-person meetings. The MC meets regularly, and additional meetings are organized at any time when needed. When applicable, the meetings are planned to be held in conjunction with the consortium meetings. In addition, close cooperation is sustained via email. Especially during the first year of the project, the meetings will be held frequently to kick-start the project work effectively. Later, if it seems that as regular meetings are no longer necessary, it may be agreed that the meetings are arranged less often. More details on the meeting practices can be found in Chapter 4.2 of this document.

4.1.5 Advisory Board

An **AB** is established to involve external stakeholders. The AB follows and advises the project in the exploitation of the results. The AB assists the project in self-evaluation based on the reports and plans.

The AB will be formed by selected external experts. The selection of candidates was conducted in the first GenA meeting in Espoo, Finland, on the 3rd of May. The approved candidates will be invited to become AB members by the CO.

The experts are aware that they may, while working for the AB, gain access to confidential information concerning the project results and the project participants. Therefore, a Non-Disclosure Agreement (NDA) will be signed with each AB member. The CO will take care of the NDAs.

The detailed working practices of the AB shall be agreed upon by the end of the second GenA. The CO will chair the AB meetings.

4.2 Working practices

4.2.1 Internal communication

Most internal communication of the consortium takes place via **emails and meetings**. VTT has established the following three **email lists** to facilitate the cooperation:

- Consortium-wide email list for all consortium members mentioned in the ADMIRAL contact details Excel document
- General Assembly email list for the GenA members and deputies
- Management Committee email list for the MC members and deputies.

The lists can be used to ensure that information reaches the necessary project members. As the email lists are sustained based on the contact information submitted to the *Consortium contact information* Excel sheet, it is vital that each Beneficiary makes sure that their contact details are always correct and up-to-date.

The meeting practicalities are addressed in the next sections of the deliverable.

4.2.2 Meetings

One of the central working practices of the management bodies of the consortium is meetings. The list of regular meetings as defined in the Consortium Agreement can be found in Table 5. The table also includes information on who should participate in which meeting, how often they are organized, by whom, and for what purpose.

Table 5 ADMIRAL regular meetings

Type	Tasks	Host/Chair	Mandatory participants	Optional participants	Occurrence	Format
Kick-off	Launch of project	CO	All Beneficiaries' representatives and key persons	Other consortium members and Project Officer	3.–4.5.2023	In-person
Consortium	Progress monitoring, status updates, planning of future tasks, etc.	As agreed by the GenA	Necessary Beneficiaries' representatives	Other consortium members and Project Officer	3 times a year	In-person
General Assembly	Make strategic decisions regarding the project and responsibilities of consortium members	CO	One representative of each consortium beneficiary organization or represented by deputy	Deputies and other members of consortium	Together with consortium meetings or as necessary	In-person or online

Management Committee	Coordinate the daily work of the project, risk assessment,	CO	CO, WPLs, and Pilot Leaders or represented by deputy	Deputies	Monthly	Mainly online
Advisory Board	Providing information and advise	CO	Co, AB members (to be nominated by the GenA)	-	Once every 6 months	As agreed
WP specific	Organise the WP-related work, delegate tasks	WPL	WP Leader, related Task Leaders	Other consortium members	As necessary	Mainly online
Review meetings with EC	Review the results of the reporting period	CO	PO (CINEA), CO, WP leaders	Other consortium members	2 weeks before submitting periodic reports	As agreed

The host in charge of organising an event or meeting is responsible for arranging the related practicalities, with the help of the CO. In case of in-person meetings or events, the responsibilities of the organiser can include, for example,

- the preparation of the agenda and schedule together with the CO
- booking the venues and the catering
- taking care of the technical arrangements, including for a hybrid connection if needed
- providing a pre-information package to the invitees, including addresses, logistics, other travelling guidance
- taking general minutes of the meeting
- collecting signed participation lists

In case of online meetings or events, the host should, for example,

- send an Outlook meeting invitation with the online meeting link and agenda well in time (when relevant, check the CA)
- prepare the meeting materials
- take the minutes

After the meeting, the host should distribute the minutes along with the meeting materials as stated in the CA. The materials should be stored in the ADMIRAL Teams Group in the files of the designated WP channel.

The costs of the event are paid by the lead organiser. The eligibility of costs is determined by each organisation's travel regulations and event organisation guidelines. Typically, eligible costs may include, for example, the venue charges, lunches, coffee break servings, as well as working dinner. Please note that a working dinner should have a clear agenda and minutes. Costs related to accommodation, travel, and daily allowance (if any) of the participants are covered directly by the Beneficiaries' own budgets.

4.2.3 Continuous improvement approach

The CO has proposed a continuous improvement -approach, and all beneficiaries committed to this in the ADMIRAL kick-off meeting. In practice, this approach means that everyone is expected to provide comments and suggestions if they come across good practices that could be implemented in the project or identify something that should be done differently.

In case of disputes, the consortium is strongly committed to solving them amicably on as a low level as possible. In such cases, the CO should always be informed without delay in order to make sure that appropriate actions are taken, and the issue can be solved as soon as possible.

4.3 Information management

4.3.1 File repository

The ADMIRAL documents are kept in the **project file repository in Microsoft Teams Group** which is administered by VTT. All consortium members have access to the Teams platform. While ensuring the information security aspects, all project documents are located in Teams. The documents include e.g., the project reference documents (see next chapter), up-to-date contact information of the project members, meeting slides and minutes, WP-related information and documents, and material for external communication (e.g., logo files and templates). The Teams environment enables members to share joint documents and develop them together. Teams will also be used to organise the project's online meetings. In addition, there is a dedicated Teams Channel for the General Assembly.

The general ADMIRAL data management practices will be defined in detail in the deliverable D1.3 Data management plan. The plan will be updated throughout the project. Moreover, the consortium has appointed a Data Manger, Jukka Kääriäinen from VTT, who will oversee the data management procedures in the project.

4.3.2 Reference documents

The **Grant Agreement (GA)** is the funding agreement between the Funding Agency and the beneficiaries. The GA forms the legal basis for the implementation of the project. It sets out the rights and obligations and the terms and conditions applicable to the grant awarded to the beneficiaries for implementing the action set out in the GA. The GA was signed between the Funding Agency and the CO of the project (VTT), and the other beneficiaries became contract partners by signing the Accession Form to the GA. The GA includes detailed information about the project implementation and should, thus, be treated as a confidential document. You can always access the GA from the Funding & Tenders Portal or the Project Teams Group.

Annex I of the Grant Agreement is the Description of the Action, i.e., the project. It contains a detailed description of the planned research and activities. The content is divided into Part A (technical details) and Part B (project description).

Any major changes to the project must be approved through an official **Amendment to the Grant Agreement**. The Commission determines when Amendments are required. For example, an Amendment is needed when adding a new beneficiary to the consortium, changing the duration of the action or the reporting periods, or making significant modifications to the Description of Action (GA

Annex I). The CO is responsible for contacting the Project Officer regarding any planned Amendment requests and for carrying them out. The Amendment process is not to be taken lightly, as it can be a laborious and lengthy process and there are no guarantees of the amendment request being accepted. Thus, in case of foreseen changes, they should be brought to the attention of the CO as soon as possible.

The **Consortium Agreement (CA)** is an internal agreement within the consortium, signed between the project beneficiaries. The CA specifies the commitments among the beneficiaries in more detail to the provisions specified in the GA, such as, but not limited to, financial issues, payments, management, decision-making, conflict resolution and intellectual property rights and liability. The CA includes detailed information about the project implementation and should, thus, be treated as a confidential document. You can always get access to the CA in the Project Teams Group.

The **Project Quality Management Plan (PQMP)**, i.e., the present document, serves as a guidance to the ADMIRAL project and a quality management guide through the project execution, the collaboration in the consortium, and the dissemination of results. The document should be understood as an internal plan and a reference source. The PQMP is a dynamic document that may be revised and updated during the project duration. As stated before, in case of inconsistency between different key documentation of the project, the following order of precedence should be applied: (1) Grant Agreement, (2) Consortium Agreement, (3) PQMP.

5 Reporting practices

5.1 Reporting periods and general guidelines

The total project duration is 36 months, with the effective starting date being 1.5.2023 and final date being 30.4.2026. As stated in the Grant Agreement, this time is split into two equal-length, 18-month long **Reporting Periods (RP)**:

- 1) The first RP is M1–M18, i.e., 1.5.2023–30.10.2024
- 2) The second RP is M18–M36, i.e., 1.11.2024–30.4.2026

The reporting principles are set in the Grant Agreement Article 21 Reporting. During the reporting periods, **continuous reporting** is carried out. In practice, this means that all project deliverables, milestones, publications, and other reportable material is to be uploaded to the European Commission's **Funding & Tenders Portal** according to their scheduled deadlines.

The continuous reporting is interrupted only at the end of each reporting period for the preparation and submission of the **Official Periodic Reports**. The CO is responsible for advising the Beneficiaries of their reporting duties, requesting the Beneficiaries' input, and compiling the technical reports in time. Each beneficiary is responsible for delivering the requested technical material and financial report on time.

The periodic reports include **technical and financial parts**:

- 1) The **technical part** includes an overview of the implementation of the action which is compiled by **Part A and Part B**, as follows:
 - a. **Part A includes all the technical information** that has been submitted to the portal throughout the continuous reporting, i.e., the deliverables, milestones, risks, etc. The CO is responsible for making sure that, at the time of submitting the report, the portal is up to date.
 - b. **Part B is a narrative description of the progress** of the project. The CO compiles the report with the help of the Beneficiaries (in particular, WP Leaders), and submits it to the portal as a PDF document.

- 2) The **financial part** of the reporting includes a statement on the use of the personnel costs, associated person months and other possible direct or subcontracting costs. **Each Beneficiary is responsible for filling their own financial report**, submitting it to the portal and signing it on time.

Roughly **two weeks before the reporting deadline**, the CO organises a **review meeting** with the WP Leaders and the CINEA Project Officer to have an overview of the reporting data. The meeting will be arranged either online or in-person, as agreed with the PO and the WP Leaders. If also other consortium members have a significant responsibility in the reporting data, they are also welcomed to join the meeting. After the meeting, once all of the information has been finalised and submitted to the portal, the **CO submits the periodic report as a whole**.

More details on the reporting will be provided by the CO closer to the end of each reporting period.

5.2 Project deliverables

Deliverables are **contractual obligations of the Grant Agreement** which the Consortium must submit to the EC as proof of the project’s progress. A list of deliverables as per the Description of Action (DoA) can be found in Table 6. More details on the deliverables, such as the deliverable descriptions, can be found in the GA.

Please note that the most recent and up-to-date list of deliverables is always the one in the Funding and Tenders Portal. Additional tasks or deliverables might appear during the project duration (e.g., at the request of the EU Project Officer).

Table 6 List of deliverables in order of due date

Del No	WP No	Title	Lead Bene.	Type	Dissem. level	Due date
D1.1	WP1	Project Quality Management Plan PQMP	VTT	R	PU	30/06/2023 (M2)
D1.2	WP1	Ethics Plan	VTT	OTHER	PU	31/07/2023 (M3)
D1.3	WP1	Project Data Management Plan PDMP v1	VTT	DMP	SEN	31/10/2023 (M6)
D3.1	WP3	Horizontal collaboration business models	VTT	R	PU	31/10/2023 (M6)
D7.1	WP7	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan v1	Steinbeis	R	SEN	31/10/2023 (M6)
D5.1	WP5	Pilot implementation plan	VTT	R	SEN	31/12/2023

						(M8)
D2.2	WP2	Different transport modes and their sustainability	LNEC	R	PU	30/04/2024 (M12)
D1.4	WP1	Project Data Management Plan PDMP v2	VTT	DMP	SEN	31/10/2024 (M18)
D2.3	WP2	Intelligent operations systems and new technologies for intermodal logistics optimization,	LNEC	R	PU	31/10/2024 (M18)
D3.2	WP3	Drivers and barriers of collaboration in logistics networks	CERTH	R	PU	31/10/2024 (M18)
D7.4	WP7	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan v2	Steinbeis	R	SEN	31/10/2024 (M18)
D6.1	WP6	Impact Assessment Framework, KPIs and Prioritization	CTLup	R	PU	31/12/2024 (M20)
D2.4	WP2	Sustainability Maturity Model	CERTH	R	PU	31/03/2025 (M23)
D5.2	WP5	Summary of pilots	VTT	R	SEN	31/10/2025 (M30)
D7.3	WP7	Report on IPR/Exploitation Workshops	Steinbeis	R	SEN	31/10/2025 (M30)
D2.1	WP2	Stakeholder analysis matrix	UPM	R	PU	31/12/2025 (M32)
D3.3	WP3	The concept of multimodal market-place and innovation plat-form functionality	VTT	R	PU	31/12/2025 (M32)
D5.3	WP5	Pilot evaluation summary report	VTT	R	PU	31/12/2025 (M32)
D6.2	WP6	Energy consumption, user experience and socio-economic impact assessment	CERTH	R	PU	28/02/2026 (M32)
D1.5	WP1	Project Data Management Plan PDMP v3	VTT	DMP	SEN	30/04/2026 (M36)
D4.1	WP4	Smart Multimodal marketplace	AWA	DEM	SEN	30/04/2026 (M36)
D6.3	WP6	Overall Impact Assessment of Project Results and Cross-Analysis of Pilots	CTLup	R	PU	30/04/2026 (M36)
D7.2	WP7	Report on Dissemination, Community Building and Training Activities	UPM	DEC	PU	30/04/2026 (M36)
D7.5	WP7	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan v3	Steinbeis	R	SEN	30/04/2026 (M36)

5.3 Deliverable preparation and review process

The deliverable preparation and review process was agreed in the first GenA meeting which was held in Espoo, Finland, on the 3rd of May 2023.

Each deliverable is led by a **Lead Beneficiary** that has the main responsibility on the preparation of the deliverable (coordinates the deliverable preparation process, collects relevant information from other Beneficiaries, prepares the first draft according to the consortium feedback, etc.). The Leader is responsible for the quality and timely preparation of the deliverable.

The first draft of the deliverable is reviewed by the whole consortium and, in particular, the **primary and secondary reviewer** organisations. The primary and secondary reviewers are selected well in

advance on a voluntary basis. The reviewers are in charge of quality-proofing the deliverable. They are expected to provide concrete feedback and, where relevant, suggestions for changes to the text.

The reviewers for the first upcoming deliverables were agreed in the GenA meeting as follows:

Del No	WP No	Title	Lead Bene.	Primary reviewer	Secondary reviewer	Due date
D1.1	WP1	Project Quality Management Plan PQMP	VTT	Steinbeis	CERTH	30/06/2023 (M2)
D1.2	WP1	Ethics Plan	VTT	Steinbeis	CERTH	31/07/2023 (M3)
D1.3	WP1	Project Data Management Plan PDMP v1	VTT	NORM	LNEC	31/10/2023 (M6)
D3.1	WP3	Horizontal collaboration business models	VTT	CERTH	UPM	31/10/2023 (M6)
D7.1	WP7	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan v1	Steinbeis	CTLup	SOLV	31/10/2023 (M6)

According to the GenA decision, the Lead Beneficiary should follow the following deliverable preparation process and timeline:

- 1) **Begin early:** The Lead Beneficiary starts preparing the deliverable early in advance. The timeline can vary depending on the requirements of the deliverable. If necessary, the Lead Beneficiary requests input from other Beneficiaries with clear instructions and a timeline.
- 2) **First version completed:** The Lead shares the first version of the deliverable with the consortium a minimum of **4–6 weeks prior to the deliverable deadline**.
- 3) **Reviewer feedback:** The reviewer (and the rest of the consortium) is given a minimum of 1–2 weeks to review the deliverable and provide comments.
- 4) **Refinement of deliverable based on feedback:** The Lead Beneficiary finalises the deliverable based on the received comments.
- 5) **Final version to CO:** The Lead Beneficiary sends the final version to the CO a minimum of **2 weeks before the deadline**.
- 6) **Submission to EU portal:** The CO does the final review and submits the deliverable to the EU Portal **by the deadline set in the Grant Agreement**.

Should the Lead or contributing Beneficiaries face any challenges with the set timeline, they are requested to contact the CO Team immediately.

5.4 Project milestones

Milestones mark the **central achievements** that need to be completed along the way of the project in order to ensure its timely progress. ADMIRAL has set 10 milestones that are listed in Table 7.

Table 7 List of Milestones in order of due date

MS No.	WP	Title	Means of verification	Lead Bene.	Due date
1	WP2	The first version for sustainability framework for pilots	Document to deliver pilot leaders	LNEC	31/10/2023 (M6)
2	WP5	Pilots ready for kick-off	Pilots have concrete plans, chronogram, KPIs, enabling technologies and solutions identified	VTT	29/02/2024 (M10)
3	WP2	Second version of framework to Impact assessment WP	Document to deliver T6.1 participants	LNEC	30/04/2024 (M12)
4	WP3	Initial concept for multimodal platform is developed (as a part of T3.5)	Document to deliver for WP4	AWA	30/04/2024 (M12)
5	WP7	Hackathon is organized	A hackathon event has been organized	AWA	30/06/2024 (M14) ²
6	WP5	Standalone solutions are piloted	All pilots successfully piloted the solutions	VTT	31/01/2025 (M21)
7	WP4	Initial functionalities for their multimodal marketplace	Demonstration	AWA	30/04/2025 (M24)
8	WP6	initial versions of T6.2-4 results are in use	A workshop will be analyzed, several interviews (at least 30 participants)	CTLup	30/04/2025 (M24)
9	WP7	Developer ecosystem partners secured	30 developer partners total	AWA	30/04/2025 (M24)
10	WP5	Confidential pilot reports finished	All pilots have provided a summary report of the conducted test, results, findings, etc.	VTT	31/07/2025 (M27)

Each milestone requires certain actions or project phases to be completed. The **Lead Beneficiary** responsible for completing the milestone, including the task(s) mentioned as means of verification. Once completed, **the Lead Beneficiary saves the evidence of the means of verification to the ADMIRAL Teams Group and informs the CO of the achieved milestone.** The CO reports the milestone completed in the Funding & Tenders Portal.

5.5 Keeping records

As stated in **Grant Agreement Article 18**, each Beneficiary must keep adequate records and other supporting documentation to prove the implementation of the action and costs declared as eligible. These records can include, for example, contracts, subcontracts, invoices, and accounting documents.

All records must be kept for **five years after the payment of the balance** in case of any audits.

² The due date of Milestone 5 is postponed from Month 12 to Month 14 of the project. The postponement has been agreed with the Project Officer and is officially approved in the first Amendment to the Grant Agreement which was launched on the 24th of May 2023.

6 Notes on communication, dissemination and exploitation

The ADMIRAL communication, dissemination, and exploitation (CDE) principles and actions will be agreed upon and implemented as part of WP7 *Communication, dissemination and exploitation*. The WP is led by Steinbeis, and all partners are to have an active role in implementing the activities. The consortium will use state-of-the-art tools and channels to enhance visibility of the project by following an interactive multi-channel approach. This will allow communication in a targeted and customised manner to reach a broad stakeholder audience, including SMEs, industry, the scientific community as well as potential end-users, local authorities, policymakers, and the general public.

The CDE principles will be detailed in the project deliverable D7.1 *Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan* of which the first version will be finalised and submitted to the Funding & Tenders Portal by the end of Month 6 of the project.

In this document, we concentrate in providing an overview and guidelines for some of the central CDE aspects in the project.

6.1 Open Science under Horizon Europe

The ADMIRAL publishing and dissemination is built on the **Open Science Policy** requirements stated in the Grant Agreement. Open Science refers to the practice of providing online access to scientific information that is free of charge to the end-user and reusable. Papers on ADMIRAL research results will be submitted to high impact peer-reviewed journals, offering suitable Open Access options. More details on these requirements can be found in the **Grant Agreement Article 17** *Communication, Dissemination, Open Science and Visibility*.

6.2 Templates

As part of WP7, the Steinbeis team has produced project **templates for deliverables and PowerPoint presentations**. The templates have been drafted for the convenience of the consortium to ensure a coherent project visual identity, to unify the project documentation, and to aid with, e.g., starting the deliverable drafting process.

The templates are stored in the project Teams Group and will be available for everyone throughout the project duration.

6.3 Publications and presentations

During the project and for a period of 1 year after the end of the project, the dissemination of own results, e.g., publications and presentations, will be subject to the procedure of Article 17.4 and Annex 5 of the Grant Agreement as well as the Consortium Agreement Article 8.4 *Dissemination*.

Before any type of dissemination activity, the beneficiaries have the obligation of giving prior notice of any planned publication or conference presentation. Similarly, if a partner would object a publication or presentation, they should respect the given deadlines. The timeframes are presented in Table 8.

Table 8 Deadlines for prior notice and objections of publications and presentations

	Prior notice deadline	Objection deadline
Publication	30 days	14 days
Presentation	10 days	7 days

The **prior notice should be given in writing via email** to the consortium, and the possible objection on the planned publication shall be made by written notice to the CO and the beneficiary/ies proposing the dissemination.

An objection is justified if

- a) the protection of the objecting Party's Results or Background would be adversely affected, or
- b) the objecting Party's legitimate interests in relation to its Results or Background would be significantly harmed, or
- c) the proposed publication includes Confidential Information of the objecting Party.

The objection must include a precise request for necessary modifications.

If no objection is made within the time limit stated above, the publication is permitted. More details can be found in the CA Article 8.4.

After the dissemination activity has taken place, e.g., an article has been published, the main responsible person, e.g., author(s), should announce the publication without delays to the dedicated Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation -document administered by Steinbeis. The Beneficiaries are responsible for making sure that the file is up to date and that the necessary information submitted is correct. Based on the filled information, the CO reports the dissemination activity e.g., project publications, in the EU Portal's Continuous reporting module.

6.4 Ownership and Access Rights

The Ownership and Access Rights are defined in the Grant Agreement (Article 16 *Intellectual property rights (IPR)* and Annex 5 *Confidentiality and Security*) and Consortium Agreement.

All information in whatever form or mode of communication, which is disclosed by a Beneficiary in connection with ADMIRAL, and which has been explicitly marked as "confidential" at the time of disclosure, is to be treated as **Confidential Information**. For a period of **5 years after the end of the project**, all participants undertake a commitment of non-disclosure as follows:

- not to use Confidential Information otherwise than for the purpose for which it was disclosed
- not to disclose Confidential Information without the prior written consent by the Disclosing Beneficiary
- to ensure that internal distribution of Confidential Information by a Recipient shall take place on a strict need-to-know basis
- to return to the Disclosing Party, or destroy, on request all Confidential Information that has been disclosed to the Recipients including all copies thereof and to delete all information

stored in a machine-readable form to the extent practically possible. The Recipients may keep a copy to the extent it is required to keep, archive, or store such Confidential Information because of compliance with applicable laws and regulations or for the proof of on-going obligations provided that the Recipient complies with the confidentiality obligations herein contained with respect to such copy.

More details on non-disclosure of information can be found in the Consortium Agreement, Section 10.

6.5 Acknowledgement of funding

The communication, dissemination, open science, and visibility requirements of the project are stated in the Grant Agreement (Article 17 and Annex 5). In particular, please note that all communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the project (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant **must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement** (translated into local languages, where appropriate):

The EU emblem can be found in Teams in the “General” channel’s “Templates” folder as well as following [this link](#). The emblem must remain distinct and separate and cannot be modified by adding other visual marks, brands, or text.

Apart from the emblem, no other visual identity or logo may be used to highlight EU support. When displayed in association with other logos (e.g., of beneficiaries or sponsors), the emblem must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the other logos.

In addition, any communication or dissemination activity related to the action **must** indicate the following **disclaimer** (translated into local languages where appropriate):

Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the granting authority CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Please make sure that these principles are followed in all ADMIRAL communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities, whenever possible. Otherwise, the activity (and its financial consequences) cannot be reported to the EC as part of the project.

7 Risk management

The ADMIRAL Consortium aims to foresee and tackle critical risks in the implementation as early on as possible through set risk management procedures as follows:

- The WP leaders are responsible for following the progress of their respective WPs.
- All members of the consortium are responsible for reporting any identified risks or deviations from Description of Action to the CO.
- The 'Critical Risks' mentioned in the Grant Agreement will be reviewed in GenA meetings on a minimum of twice per reporting period and whenever needed. Accordingly, the critical risks and their proposed mitigations are updated regularly in the Funding & Tenders Portal.
- An "owner" will be nominated for each of the identified risks in order to ensure the timely monitoring of the risk.
- The consequences of the risks, including possible deviations from the project plan, will be evaluated by the MC and GenA. Corrective measures will be discussed and implemented together with the consortium and/or participant in question.
- In the case of defaulting parties, the CA defines the measures to be taken. The GenA will decide the needed sanctions and the CO will carry them out and inform the European Commission.

8 Ethics management

The ADMIRAL ethics principles are set in Deliverable D1.2 *Ethics Plan* as well as the GA requirements. The ADMIRAL consortium is strictly committed to following the highest ethical principles throughout the project.

9 Conclusions

This deliverable portrays the key aspects of the ADMIRAL project's management and practicalities to ensure the high-quality, coherent and timely execution of the project. VTT as CO of the project is responsible for creating the PQMP, updating it when necessary, and leading the consortium accordingly. All ADMIRAL consortium members are committed to studying the plan with care and acting according to the set-out principles and practices.

Should any consortium member have suggestions for improving the plan, they should contact the CO Team promptly. The latest version of the deliverable will always be available in the document repository of the project.